

Research Article

India and Brics Summit - Trade, Technology and Alignment Strategic

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Abstract

India's engagement with BRICS and its broader strategic positioning reflect a complex mix of historical, economic, and geopolitical factors. Initially motivated by a desire to counterbalance U.S. dominance, India's transition from RIC to BRICS represented a strategic shift towards multipolarity. Today, India balances its relations with China and Russia while strengthening ties with Western nations, including the U.S., Europe, and Japan. India's involvement in BRICS, despite its potential anti-Western tilt, is part of a pragmatic strategy to manage China's influence and expand global partnerships. This approach, known as "multi-alignment," includes active roles in the Quad and G7 and emphasizes technological and economic collaboration. India's rise as a global player is underscored by its growing ties with Africa and its cost-effective space program. Overall, India's foreign policy is characterized by a pragmatic pursuit of national interests, aiming to shape a balanced global order amidst evolving international dynamics.

Keywords: BRICS, RIC (Russia, India, China), Indian Nuclear Program, China-Russia Relations, Quad, G7, Strategic Autonomy, Trade Agreements, European Union Relations, China's Regional Hegemony G20 Summit

Introduction

To better understand India's agenda within the BRICS, we must take a historical perspective. India's initial engagement with the precursors of the BRICS, then known by the acronym RIC (Russia, India, and China), dates back to the 1990s. The main driver of this collaboration was the shared concern for the unipolar world order and the need to defend multipolarity. Indeed, Russia helped persuade India that, by working in unison with Beijing and Moscow, it could pave the way toward a more balanced global landscape within the RIC.¹

But India approached this partnership with caution. At that time, she was trying-with difficulty—to build her relationship with the United States, walking a tightrope. This bilateral relationship was hampered by two major issues. Firstly, the contentious Kashmir issue, which the Clinton administration wanted to resolve, and secondly, the nuclear issue: the United States

¹Chaulia, Sreeram. "In spite of the spite: An Indian view of China and India in BRICS." *Global policy* 12.4 (2021): 519-523.

considered it essential for its non-proliferation policy to roll back the Indian nuclear program. For India, these issues directly challenge its territorial integrity and security interests.²

Linkage of India's current challenges with Chinese & Russia

By opening its economy to the United States, India recognized the need to foster an alternative relationship. In this context, he joined the RIC initiative. It is true that India has not developed such an integrated partnership with other countries; although there is great cooperation, India has started to work more closely with Russia and China.³

During the 2000s, India observed the growing ambition of Russia and China to expand the BRICS forum, adopting a clearly anti-American and anti-Western stance. At the same time, New Delhi has continued to improve its relations with the West, particularly the United States. Today, as India's position within the BRICS has evolved, Washington has become its main partner. In fact, most of India's current challenges are associated with Chinese power, with one important break.⁴

Relevancy of BRICS forum for India

The complexity of international relations means that India cannot simply withdraw from the BRICS, just as France cannot simply withdraw from NATO. Despite the difficulties that are emerging, New Delhi remains a member of the BRICS coalition. At the same time, India has no compelling reason to align itself with the anti-Western agenda that Russia and China appear to be promoting within the group. In fact, India's main concern is to ensure that the BRICS does not become an anti-Western platform. Rather, India's interest is to limit China's dominance and build strong alliances with the United States, Europe, and Japan to effectively counter China.⁵

Another key aspect of India's evolving position is its competition with Beijing for influence in the South. Contrary to some misconceptions that present this competition as a revival of non-alignment, India is in fact striving to secure its place on the world stage. Historically, it has made significant investments in the South, unlike China, which has never been part of the non-alignment movement but has instead followed a "G77+1" strategy; India is determined to protect its investments and compete with China for influence.

India aims to forming robust alliances with the Countries

In the context of the recent BRICS summit, India's expansion of the group now includes countries that maintain alliances with the United States. Thus, this expansion is not inherently hostile to the West. Countries like Egypt, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates are interested in negotiating with the United States, not in leaving the Western bloc. Its relations with the United States can vary considerably from one administration to another, underscoring

²Cooper, Andrew F. "China, India and the pattern of G20/BRICS engagement: differentiated ambivalence between 'rising'power status and solidarity with the Global South." *Third World Quarterly* 42.9 (2021): 1945-1962.

³Kumar, Rajan. "India and BRICS." *Locating BRICS in the Global Order*. Routledge India, 2022. 207-220.

⁴Kirton, John, and Marina Larionova. "The first fifteen years of the BRICS." *International Organisations Research Journal* 17.2 (2022): 7-30.

⁵Kumar, Pramod. "15th BRICS summit: key takeaways and their relevance." *The Round Table* 112.5 (2023): 549-550.

his pragmatism. Recent events, such as negotiations between the United States and Saudi Arabia to normalize their relations and bring them closer to Israel, confirm this point.⁶

Therefore, India's position within the BRICS is essentially from the realistic angle of pursuing its national interests. We must see all member countries as pragmatic actors, each with their own objectives within the BRICS. Far from being immersed in a Sino-Russian conspiracy, they are all participating in a game of nuances in which this organizational platform serves different objectives for different nations. Realism, then, is what defines India's role within the BRICS and its broader diplomatic Strategy on the world stage. A group of countries that use this platform as a bargaining chip in their relations with the United States is now clearly emerging, ranging from Egypt to Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates.⁷

The Indian approach to global affairs is indeed multifaceted. The Indian Ministry of External Affairs adopts the concept of "multi-alignment" as a strategy to diversify its global partnerships. On the other hand, India pursues nationalist objectives as a realistic actor in international politics. In this complex panorama, it faces unique challenges, among which the management of historical rivalries with its two main neighbors, China and Pakistan, stands out. While the latter's weight in India's security concerns has diminished over time, China, on the other hand, looms as the most important challenge, especially since it has emerged as Pakistan's main protector and promoter.⁸

As a member of the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (Quad) and regular invitee to G7 forums, India has strategically moved closer to the United States in response to China. We have considerably strengthened our bilateral ties with the United States, encompassing not only security but also economic integration. The depth and breadth of our economic ties with the West are often overlooked. The United States is our main trading partner, followed closely by Europe. India also maintains close ties with English-speaking countries such as the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand. This economic alignment underscores India's growing engagement with Western economies.⁹

India's national interests and strategic objectives converge with those of Western countries; our common goal is to establish an Asian order that is not dominated by a single power. In this context, India's diversification efforts involve moving away from its historical dependence on Russia, especially in the defense sector. It recognizes its unique position as a society deeply linked to the West, culturally, intellectually, and otherwise. It does not see the West as a threat but as a partner for cooperation. However, and this is the key to understanding its diplomatic position, India will not be content with being submissive or subordinate to the West.¹⁰

⁶Anand, Vinod. "Dynamics from BRICS Countries—A Perspective on BRICS Development Strategies: Prospects and Issues." *The Coordination Of Brics Development Strategies Towards Shared Prosperity* (2019): 67.

⁷Stuenkel, Oliver. *The BRICS and the future of global order*. Lexington books, 2020.

⁸Hooijmaaijers, Bas. "The brics countries' bilateral economic relations, 2009 to 2019: Between rhetoric and reality." *Sage Open* 11.4 (2021): 2158.

⁹Basile, Elisabetta, and Claudio Cecchi. "Will the BRICS succeed in leading the way to sustainable development?." *Rivista di Studi Politici Internazionali* 85.2 (338 (2018): 223-234.

¹⁰Pedersen, Jørgen Dige. "India—Dreaming with BRICS?." *The International Political Economy of the BRICS*. Routledge, 2019. 165-179.

India strategically moves

In essence, India's approach aligns with the idea of a shared and balanced power structure, similar to the scenario of the early 20th century, when the American, British, and French powers worked together in an evolutionary dynamic. India aims to reach an agreement with the West not in the form of a traditional alliance like NATO but as part of a broader convergence of interests and values. This unique and dynamic relationship represents a historic opportunity for India and Western nations to shape the world order and address common challenges in the Eastern Hemisphere. It is a partnership based on mutual respect, shared values, and recognition of each other's sovereignty.¹¹

The escalation of tensions with China has recently consolidated with the release of an official map covering the disputed regions. India has also displayed an expansionist map in its new Parliament building. Xi Jinping's decision not to attend the G20 seems to show that we have entered a new dimension of diplomatic escalation.¹²

Historically, the concept of Asian solidarity, an aspiration for a post-Western world order in which a decolonized Asia could forge a new path based on its principles, rooted India's foreign policy. By adopting this vision, India sought to befriend all of Asia, including China, while distancing itself from the West. This became a fundamental principle of India's early foreign policy. But this strategy has not been very successful. China, in particular, proved difficult to approach, causing a whole host of complications with the original plan. At the same time, the West, especially during the Cold War, supported countries like Pakistan and, later, China. This divergence of strategies between befriending Asia and distancing itself from the West was not ultimately in India's interest.¹³

The turning point came when China began to pursue its own goals of regional hegemony, seeking to establish a stable regional order in partnership with the United States and the West. This shift in China's priorities fundamentally clashed with India's vision. It is important to note that India supported China's recognition in the 1950s, when many Western countries were hesitant to get involved. India declined the United States' offer of a Security Council seat, asserting that China was the rightful representative of the Chinese people. India sincerely tried to foster a strong partnership with China, but China had a different vision, one that emphasized its own greatness and its unique role in shaping the Asian order.¹⁴

In light of these historic events and changing circumstances, India has adopted a more pragmatic approach. He is increasingly aware that he may have overestimated her problems with the West in the past while underestimating the challenges posed by China. Today, India values its partnership with the West more than ever and recognizes the need to deter China from further expansionism in Asia.¹⁵

¹¹Srinivas, Junuguru. "Rise of the BRICS and Changing World Order: Role of India and China." India and China. Routledge India, 2020. 68-85.

¹²Rajagopalan, Rajeswari Pillai. "Contradictions grow amid another BRICS summit." (2020).

¹³Rahman, Nida, and Sheena Rehman. "BRICS Diplomacy: India-China Relations." *Manag Econ Res J* 7.4 (2021).

¹⁴Niu, Haibin, and Sheng Hong. "A Chinese perspective: Will China-India friction paralyze the BRICS?." *Global Policy* 12.4 (2021): 524-528.

¹⁵Kumar, Pramod. "15th BRICS summit: key takeaways and their relevance." *The Round Table* 112.5 (2023): 549-550.

India and its pragmatic approach

The world is facing a profound crisis of multilateralism, amplified by the war in Ukraine, during the BRICS Summit. At the same time, the reign of multilateral economic agreements appears to have peaked. The rules that underpin the global economic system, especially since China's entry into the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2001, The United States is attempting to revise these rules to better serve its interests, but there is little agreement between the United States and China on these issues. Added to this is the fundamental divergence between Russia and the West over the European order and between China and Western nations over the world economic order. It is symptomatic that, even in Asia, China and its neighbors cannot agree on the regional order. However, in the midst of this multilateral crisis, India is experiencing a relative rise in power. It is poised to become the world's third-largest economy by the end of the decade.¹⁶

Much attention is being paid to the question of whether there will be a joint declaration at the end of this summit. The reality, however, is that the G20 alone cannot resolve the complex issues raised in Europe in the wake of the Russian invasion of Ukraine. While diplomatic efforts and public opinion mobilization may result in condemnation, the decision of twenty leaders to sit outside Europe and wait for agreement will not resolve the core issue.¹⁷

The G20 will primarily deal with economic issues, and India's contribution in this regard is substantial. He has worked with the United States and European countries on global tax reforms, which could yield positive results at the summit. India is also actively participating in discussions on trade facilitation and technology, leveraging its experience in digital public infrastructure. India can congratulate itself for not allowing issues like Ukraine or WTO disputes to dominate the summit agenda. Instead, he focused on other issues, even seeking support from Russia. India's approach seeks to establish a consensus around certain elements of multilateralism that are sustainable. With the challenges facing multilateralism, India is willing to collaborate with like-minded Western countries, such as the G7, on issues such as technology, global climate change, supply chains, essential minerals, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity. These collaborations could form the basis of a new structure of multilateralism that responds to changing global power dynamics.¹⁸

India towards the G7

Today's changing dynamics call for active participation in shaping the future of multilateralism, both within existing frameworks like the G20 and through new partnerships with like-minded nations, such as the G7. This approach reflects its determination to salvage what it can from the current multilateral order while proactively building new structures to address contemporary global challenges.¹⁹

The original idea that brought the G20 together in 2008—that all the great powers can work in harmony—has faded. At present, China seems reluctant to support even the most basic proposals from India within the G20 framework. As things stand, and unless there is a

¹⁶Trivedy, Arpita, and Moududa Khatun. "Importance of BRICS as a regional politics and policies." *GeoJournal* 88.5 (2023): 5205-5220.

¹⁷Shetiya, Rita Madanlal. "BRICS AND INDIA: Prospects and Challenges." (2024).

¹⁸Downie, Christian, and Marc Williams. "After the Paris agreement: what role for the BRICS in global climate governance?." *Global Policy* 9.3 (2018): 398-407.

¹⁹Pant, Harsh V., and Tobias Scholz. "BRICS: expiring political relevance and inspiring new coalitions." *Handbook on Global Governance and Regionalism*. Edward Elgar Publishing, 2022. 148-159.

significant change in the positions of Russia and China, which does not seem to be on the agenda, the G20 seems unlikely to fulfill its original promises. Although India will continue to participate, it may increasingly look outward. In the longer term, a trend toward unilateralism may be emerging. China's assertiveness and territorial claims on its neighbors have paralyzed one of Asia's most successful multilateral institutions, as demonstrated by the ASEAN summit, held just one day before the G20.²⁰

In the Asian context, India is already part of the Quad, actively working with its partners to reshape the region without replacing ASEAN but complementing its efforts. Similarly, India's commitment to the G7 is increasingly important. This will depend on the G7's openness to such cooperation. There has been talk of expanding the G7 to include other countries, for example, by transforming it into a G10, recognizing the need for a broader coalition of nations as the relative influence of G7 members declines. In this context, it is vital for India to explore new avenues of collaboration within the G7; this could mean rethinking and expanding areas of cooperation and creating a platform for constructive engagement with like-minded nations.²¹

India plays a central role in setting the agenda within the group, precisely to prevent it from becoming solely and overtly an anti-Western platform. Thus, there appears to be no contradiction between India's commitment to the BRICS and its closer cooperation with the G7. Furthermore, India's evolving partnerships and alignments, such as its growing closeness to France and participation in various international forums, demonstrate that India is navigating a complex and multifaceted global landscape. It is not content with being part of traditional alliances such as NATO or the G7. Rather, it recognizes, more generally, the need to foster networks of overlapping alliances and encourage individual countries to take greater responsibility for regional and global security. It is increasingly vital for India to explore new avenues of collaboration within the G7.²²

For example, Japan, the world's third-largest economy, is being invited to play a more active role in security. Germany, the world's fourth-largest economy, must contribute to European security. India, the world's fifth-largest economy, is encouraged to redouble its efforts on regional security. This approach reflects the move away from a unilateral world order or one led by a single entity: the United States. Washington's new doctrine also appears to embrace a more decentralized management of the world order, in which several countries play an important role and share responsibilities. This approach not only distributes the burden, but it also ensures greater sustainability in the management of world affairs. It recognizes that the world is increasingly complex and that addressing global challenges requires a more diverse and flexible approach.²³

India clearly recognizes that Africa holds great potential for collaboration in various areas and is actively working to strengthen its ties with the nations of that continent. Historically, India played a role in Africa during the colonial period, when Indian capital and

²⁰Chaulia, Sreeram. "In spite of the spite: An Indian view of China and India in BRICS." *Global policy* 12.4 (2021): 519-523.

²¹Verma, Raj, and Mihaela Papa. "BRICS amidst India-China rivalry." *Global Policy* 12.4 (2021): 509-513.

²²Cooper, Andrew F. "China, India and the pattern of G20/BRICS engagement: differentiated ambivalence between 'rising' power status and solidarity with the Global South." *Third World Quarterly* 42.9 (2021): 1945-1962.

²³Kumar, Pramod. "15th BRICS summit: key takeaways and their relevance." *The Round Table* 112.5 (2023): 549-550.

labor contributed to the development of modern Africa. He also provided aid and support to African countries during their post-independence struggles. This history has generated a reservoir of goodwill for India in Africa. However, when India faced economic difficulties in the second half of the 20th century, its ability to contribute to Africa's development weakened. At the same time, China became a major player in Africa thanks to its economic power and resources.²⁴

Today, India is better placed to engage with Africa on several fronts. Its trade relations with African countries are growing, and it is also forging security ties. He sees potential for greater collaboration in areas such as technology transfer, institutional development, and infrastructure construction. Overall, India's growing capabilities, both financial and military, are allowing it to play a greater role in Africa's development and security. India's commitment to the African Union and its efforts, which have led to it finally obtaining a permanent seat for the African Union within the G20, reflect this commitment.²⁵

Final Considerations

First and foremost, this mission is a feat accomplished on a minimal budget compared to other space programs. It seems to me to reflect India's ambitions in this field by attempting to convey several key messages. Firstly, India has developed a solid scientific and technological base over the years. The success of the mission highlights India's capabilities in the field of space exploration, demonstrating that it can undertake complex and ambitious projects. India is also establishing itself as a major player in the global scientific community. Finally, the profitability of your space program, which is another important achievement, India has shown that it can achieve ambitious goals while maintaining profitability. And this thrifty approach to innovation has attracted attention and admiration from the international community.²⁶

The Indian space program has always collaborated with Western scientific institutions, especially the United States and France. This collaboration underscores India's commitment to working with international partners to advance scientific knowledge and space exploration. India's ambitions in space go far beyond a simple mission. The country wants to establish a lasting presence on the Moon, start manufacturing space products, and explore deep space. India anticipates long-term growth in space technology and industry. For many Europeans, India seems to have become a global swing state, the gateway to the South, with which the conditions for a new consensus must be created.²⁷

India's approach to Europe has evolved over the years, and the Indian Ministry of External Affairs increasingly recognizes the strategic importance of relations with the Union and its member countries. While historically, India's ties focused primarily on major European powers such as Britain, France, and Germany, there is now a broader, more global approach that includes engagement with smaller European countries. India believes that it is possible to build relationships with a wide range of European nations, each of which offers its own capabilities and areas of cooperation. India has prioritized trade and economic relations with Europe. It has

²⁴Papa, Mihaela, and Raj Verma. "Scenarios for BRICS Evolution in Light of the India–China Conflict." *Global Policy* 12.4 (2021): 539-544.

²⁵Li, Li. "BRICS: a limited role in transforming the world." *Strategic Analysis* 43.6 (2019): 499-508.

²⁶Lagutina, Maria L. "BRICS in a world of regions." *Third World Thematics: A TWQ Journal* 4.6 (2019): 442-458.

²⁷Kirton, John, and Marina Larionova. "The first fifteen years of the BRICS." *International Organisations Research Journal* 17.2 (2022): 7-30.

relaunched negotiations for a free trade agreement with the EU and is also working on an agreement with the European Free Trade Association (EFTA). High-level visits by Indian leaders to the continent underline the importance of political commitment. India is also exploring opportunities for strategic cooperation with European nations. While Europe seeks to develop strategic autonomy with respect to the United States, India seeks it with respect to Russia.²⁸ Interestingly, the Indian approach is aligned with the concept of strategic autonomy, although on a very different basis from that of the Union. While Europe seeks to develop strategic autonomy in relation to the United States, India seeks to achieve it in relation to Russia. In short, this is a multifaceted approach, but it seems to me that both sides are increasingly aware of the potential for closer cooperation and are exploring ways to strengthen their relationship, especially in the areas of trade, technology, and strategic alignment.

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²⁸Kirton, John J. "Explaining the solid, strengthening success of the BRICS summit." *BRICS and Global Governance*. Routledge, 2018. 21-40.